

Multimedia Aided Classrooms in the Pedagogy of English: Problems and Plausible Solutions in the Context of the Private Universities in Bangladesh

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ABSTRACT

Teaching students in the private universities of Bangladesh using multimedia is a common issue that is discussed among teachers and students all over Bangladesh. With the advancement of technology, new accessories are invented giving tremendous progress in the pedagogy of English ensuring maximum benefits and acceptability among teachers and students. In the context of the private universities of Bangladesh, the number of multimedia accessories is not sufficient to run classes simultaneously using multimedia. There are a number of barriers that teachers and students face in a multimedia classroom that ultimately hamper their teaching and learning. Following both qualitative and quantitative methods in this study, survey questionnaires and in-depth interviews were used as instruments for data collection. In the multimedia teaching process, a teacher's personal strategy and teaching ability can design the supervision and assessment system. By implementing reforms on multimedia teaching equipment as well as quality standard evaluation of multimedia teaching, an effective supervision and evaluation system may be developed in multimedia teaching in the context of private universities in Bangladesh.

Keywords: Multimedia, Accessories, Pedagogy, Technology, EFL

1. Introduction

Multimedia aided classrooms are designed to facilitate learners than the traditional methods all over the world but in the context of private universities of Bangladesh, we observed that there are certain barriers for students and teachers that make it really difficult to receive and deliver lessons.

Tools like Pie Chart, Word Cloud, and TreeMap are used to support our claim. The TAM model by Davis explains the cognitive factors of the operability of the examined information system that is, it deals with learners' understanding as well as the use of the information from the multimedia. Pie Charts show students' responses to the various questionnaire regarding their opinion on the problems they often face in multimedia classrooms. Word Cloud helps to give a graphic representation of the most used words from the interview of the teachers and students related to the multimedia classrooms. Lastly, TreeMap is used to display all the data in a hierarchical order.

Multimedia is an exciting combination of computer hardware and software that allows one to enhance presentations by integrating video, motion graphics, audio, visuals, and text resources into an accessible desktop computer (Susikaran, 2015). Multimedia applies to computers or tablets, projectors, speakers, and other associated instruments and cables called prerequisites for using these technological devices in a real-life school. It seems like many patterns are developing. Computers are becoming readily accessible in schools across the world. Governments, educators, and parents advocate the networking of these devices, and all stages of education make long-term preparations for their use. New requirements are then set for teachers to use the technology creatively, culminating in a sharp increase in membership of associated mailing lists and the number of internet teacher training courses available (Teeler & Gray, 2000). Some private English medium schools and private universities in urban centres are seeking to use Google classrooms to upload academic tasks, submit assignments and get reviews, though peripheral organizations have no clue regarding Google Classroom. As they have no chance to be affiliated with such gadgets, they are slumping behind and trailing out of new technical development (Alam, 2018). If expertly handled and imagination, multimedia can be a very productive means of educating students at every education stage. Multimedia classrooms can be far more exciting than classes of conventional boards and markers. It is also valid, though, that not all courses can be taught using

multimedia effectively. The use of multimedia in the form of language teaching has become one of the fundamental skills that a person must possess today for the successful functioning of the class. Multimedia, in reality, has transformed all facets of the essence of schooling and language learning (Ahmed, 2018).

In the context of Bangladeshi private universities, most of the teachers are bound to take classes in traditional board and marker. This does not mean that they do not want to take classes using multimedia rather highlight some of the limitations they are unable to overcome in terms of using technology.

Teachers take classes avoiding multimedia for certain reasons in the private universities of Bangladesh. Firstly, the pressure of taking classes is high and they do not get enough time to prepare slides for efficient multimedia classes. Secondly, the limitations of accessories are high for which there is a possibility of not finding multimedia support before taking a class for all the teachers at the same time which ultimately demoralizes them not to go with multimedia classrooms. Thirdly, materials and resource support for preparing slides are so limited that they hardly find motivation in preparing slides for multimedia classrooms. Fourthly, the lack of teachers' training for preparing and taking multimedia classes is also another key factor of their avoiding multimedia classes.

Like external problems, internal problems are as many. Both teachers and students shared their views when asked regarding the problems they found while teaching and attending multimedia classes. These issues are recognized by many but not taken further to give a solution. We believe that if we can showcase these issues and come up with some possible solutions then it will be beneficial for the teachers and learners in the pedagogy of English in the multimedia-aided classrooms in Bangladesh. Therefore, this article offers some plausible and possible solutions to those hurdles and proposes some possible ways to make multimedia classes more effective.

2. Literature Review

2.1. Multimedia and an overview

Within the classroom, there has been a large selection of studies and publications on multimedia use. In the last couple of decades, managing digital classrooms and multimedia as teaching tools have been a significant

area of discussion in academia throughout the world. Several educators and scholars have spoken a lot about multimedia usage and clarified why students could use multimedia. The researchers investigated various related questions in this report to find out regarding issues with contemporary classrooms. In their study, Kern and Warschauer (2000) stress the need to utilize genuine materials that can be learned through technology, and this form of technology can be useful in addressing the demands of social, teaching, and learning needs. Their study points out that if the teachers support the students join new authentic cultures of debate, and if such groups of discourse are gradually online, it seems necessary to integrate online experiences for their societal benefit and their supposed real pedagogical importance. In generating media-rich outputs, multimedia includes the integration of media and is organized in some chunks connected by hypermedia. Learners can traverse to the educational resource in a lesser duration, attach the major aspects and build their understanding with the important insights (Hede & Hede, 2002; Parekh, 2006).

Technologically speaking, multimedia is the new technological breakthrough to be announced as the policy tool plaguing American education, also recognized as hypermedia or hypertext. Such ambitious concerns were raised earlier (Cuban, 1990), and definitely few would honestly think that immersive multimedia or emerging innovations can indeed save classrooms. Even so, multimedia is a fact and it is important to fully explore its effectiveness in the curriculum (Fan & Orey, 2001). Meskil (2005), in this regard, has defined two critical features of technology where the computer plays the most pivotal role. As with all instruments, their usage changes the ways it is perceived, performed, and connected. In digital classrooms that serve the function of educating students to promote their learning, computers are undeniably crucial. Some applications form the approach students learn, act, and connect in the classrooms, too, in any case.

Throughout the world, the usage of multimedia and different applications in teaching and learning language-based courses have become an incredible phenomenon through which the entire process of teaching and learning the basic skills of language such as listening and speaking have reached a different level. Tang (2011), in her study on the usage of multimedia in teaching language courses in China, mentions that the usage of multimedia, especially in teaching English as a language, has added a new dimension. The usage of different software and application have made language teaching and learning quite easier than past for both the teachers

and the learners. Having language labs with multimedia facilities and a multimedia network infrastructure offers an authentic and native English listening and speaking experience and allows students to provide more chances to improve their listening and speaking skills not only inside the classroom but out of class too. Teachers serve as planners, leaders, and coordinators of student listening and speech events in and out of class where students don't act as the "tape-recorder" anymore. Rather, they become engaged listeners and interpreters who are expected to undertake a set of listening and speech tasks (Tang, 2011). Thus multimedia-based teaching technique has elevated education, especially language-related ones to a certain level where both the teachers and the students have the experience of utilizing the technological aids which make everything easier for both parties.

Research done by Kasper (1997) reveals that students are motivated to compose a critical review on tasks by teaching English utilizing multimedia such as paper, movie, film, internet. Conclude, the performance of the students improved dramatically. The departmental reading and writing tests were passed by 92 percent of the candidates. Moreover, their opinion on the debates was really good. Through their capacity of using English, they show faith. They contribute this enhancement to the multimedia model because the texts teach English to them and include valuable knowledge in other subjects and allow them to find it helps to identify content so they see, hear, and learn about the subject.

Although recognizing technologies and diverse facets of technology, it still needs to consider how they should be effectively applied inside schools, meaning that students are sufficiently facilitated. Several obstacles have been noticed inside the classrooms regarding the usage of multimedia while teaching language-related courses among the private universities in Bangladesh from the viewpoints of teachers and students that need care.

2.2. Multimedia Classrooms for EFL

Using multimedia in the classes for the English courses has always been quite a difficult task for teachers in different parts of the world. Teachers have encountered many obstacles while introducing multimedia in teaching the English language in the classes. Getting proper technical supports, setting up the equipment in the classrooms, training the teachers on the usage of multimedia, teachers' preferences, familiarizing the equipment to the

students, these all became the barriers on the way of introducing multimedia-based teaching, especially for the English language classes. Fernandez Carballo-Calero (2001) in her study on EFL teachers' experience regarding the multimedia classrooms in Spain mentions that English classes are typically conducted in the traditional way, giving lecturers, writing on the board. Thus, the use of multimedia in English classes has been quite a challenge, especially in language classes. There are some more issues that can hamper the teaching process while using multimedia. As per the study done by Cummings (1995, 1996), mentioned in Blin's study (1997), there have been six major points that can be considered as the barriers that demoralize the teachers and other academic personals from utilizing the multimedia in the classrooms. However, it is not only the multimedia that the study found, rather all the other technologies in the classrooms that could have been some major threats to the teachers regarding their teaching process and attitudes. The major issues are:

i. Incentives: The feeling that they would be displaced by machines. This is a factor often figured out by Tanguay (1997), who argues that paranoia is irrational because the teaching equation would still involve a human being on both sides. What occurs, he describes, is that as it increases both the teaching and the learning ability of the pupil, the machine placed between the two human beings becomes more efficient.

ii. Understanding the technologies used in academia and education

iii. Model of teaching: The evolution of teaching process and the role of a teacher.

iv. The lack of resource access.

v. Technological challenges.

vi. Institutional traditions (curriculum, staff overload...)

Fernandez Carballo-Calero (2001) in her study, mentions the importance of having the fixed roles of the teachers in the classrooms, especially in the classrooms where the subject is English, and the teacher conducts the classes through multimedia. Besides the role of the teachers, there are significant roles of the tools. As per her study of the computer in multimedia, the classroom functions as a tool only while the teacher is present in the classroom and in charge of the classroom.

In the English classes (both language and literature), using multimedia has been a challenge for the teachers where English is not the primary language. The students also encounter several challenges regarding the same issue. However, it is the teacher, who makes the lessons and the teaching process more comprehensive for the students by using multimedia just as a tool to assist them in the classrooms.

2.3. Multimedia Classrooms in the English Classes in Bangladesh

Throughout the world, technology has become a vital pathway in the teaching and learning process in almost all levels of academic institutions. From primary schools to the public and private universities all over the world have adopted the advancements of technologies to improve the education system of the region, and the use of multimedia is one of the instances in this regard. Bangladesh is no exception in this regard. Being one of the developing countries, this country has been trying quite hard to adapt the latest technologies in almost every sphere of development. New technologies are a clear determinant in the extent multimedia and its methods are applied in a language classroom. The idea of multimedia in the academic sector of Bangladesh is not an unrealistic and far-reaching topic. Instead, it has a positive effect on curriculum advancement, digitization of the educational environment, and cooperation of the technique of education (Ahmed, 2018). Ahmed, in his research on multimedia-aided teaching in Bangladesh, mentions that the application of information and communication technologies (ICTs) is an accessible arena that has intrinsic features comparable to any other advancement in meeting citizens' needs.

The present era is defined by the significant expansion of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) and the scope of language education for learners in English as a Second Language (ESL) is a thriving and perhaps most classified issue. The application of multimedia to Bangladesh's language teaching is not so far from. Bangladesh is also at the early stage of completely adopting the idea of multimedia and is heading via a sequence of uprisings in the maximum implementation of this recently developed principle. There is a wide potential for teachers and students to use technological equipment such as laptops, overhead projectors (OHP), and classroom speakers in any single skill. Students may be able to benefit from the visual presentation of the subject in real life, listen to what video resources are playing on, and read in chorus reading passages or reading papers delivered by the instructor of the course (Ahmed, 2018).

Ahmed (2018) has figured out a few visible challenges in the multimedia aided language teaching in Bangladesh, such as deficiency in budget and limitations in the resources, gaps in the infrastructural establishments, technical support like power crisis and continuous electric supply, poor internet speed, and finally the unavailability of the well-trained teachers for the multimedia-based classes, especially for the English language and literature classes. Despite all these challenges, in most of the universities in Bangladesh, teachers are using multimedia as a teaching tool both in the English language and literature classes. Moreover, at the present day, due to the boom of modern technology, CALL (Computer Assisted Language Learning) and MALL (Mobile Assisted Language Learning) have become quite familiar amidst the students from various levels of education in Bangladesh. And these two processes of language learning help the students even outside of the class.

In our research, we found the challenges are many from both teachers' and students' perspectives regarding multimedia classrooms which need serious attention. Therefore, we not only identified the problems but also tried to give some possible solutions so that it can facilitate both teaching and learning experiences using multimedia accessories in the context of the private universities of Bangladesh.

3. Methodology

To get the best outcome and to achieve the goal with more credible findings, the current study requires a mixed-method formula. Therefore, the authors have applied both the qualitative and the quantitative methods for conducting the study. Since the study focuses on the barriers such as the imbalance of the syllabus and semester-length, lack of basic language skills knowledge, the lack of resource access, regarding the multimedia classes for the English courses (both English language and literature), it requires the opinions of both the teachers from the department of English and students from various departments including English from different private universities in Bangladesh. The questionnaire survey for the students is conducted for the quantitative portion of the study and the part of in-depth interviews with the teachers from the department of English from the different private universities in Bangladesh have been done for the qualitative part. The study has been conducted through the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) Data were analyzed using google form and pie chart where both students' and teachers' responses were taken anonymously.

3.1. Sampling

For the current study, the authors have done convenient sampling to collect data. The authors collected primary the data (for both the qualitative and quantitative parts of the study) from their own workplace and from other private universities in Bangladesh. For the questionnaire part, 100 university students have responded and 10 university teachers have been interviewed from different private universities in Bangladesh.

3.2. Data Collection

The data for the current study has been collected from both primary and secondary sources to get the answer to the research question and achieve the goal of the study. The authors here set 10 close-ended questions for the questionnaire for the students from different levels in the different private universities of Bangladesh. In total 100 university students from different private universities in Bangladesh responded through the questionnaire where the authors set 10 closed-ended questions regarding their opinions on their experience of the multimedia classes on the English courses. The questionnaire part functions as the quantitative data. The qualitative data has been collected through in-depth interview with the English teachers (lecturers, assistant professors, associate professors, and professors). The in-depth interview is one of the core processes of primary data collection. Boyce and Neale (2006) have defined an in-depth interview as a “*qualitative research technique that involves conducting intensive individual interviews with a small number of respondents to explore their perspectives on a particular idea, program, or situation.*” Due to the pandemic situation caused by the COVID-19, the authors managed to conduct the semi-structured in-depth interview with the English teachers online.

3.3. Data Triangulation

The authors have been very mindful of the credibility of the report. The data collection methods have been taken as an in-depth interview with the teachers from different private universities in Bangladesh, a survey questionnaire from the private university students, and a paper analysis showing a triangulation of the quality of the details. In addition, the report's reliability meets integrity, reliability, confirmability, and transferability (Lincoln & Guba, 1985).

3.4. Theoretical Framework

The current study has been conducted through the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM). The Technology Acceptance Model was developed by Davis (1989) and is one of the most common testing frameworks for individual users to forecast the use and acceptance by individual users of information systems and technology. TAM has been extensively researched and validated by numerous experiments investigating the conduct of specific acceptance of technology in different constructs of information systems (Surendran, 2012).

The following figure (Figure 1) demonstrates the TAM model. The opinions from both teachers and students have been analyzed through the key issues of the TAM model.

Figure 1: The TAM model by Davis (Davis, Bagozzi & Warshaw, 1989)

4. Review from the students

The review from the students have been collected through the survey questions. In the questionnaire survey, the authors received responses from 100 students for 10 questions related to the objective of the study. This part of the study presents the percentage of the opinions of the students from the questions.

i. Do you think that it hampers your understanding of the lecture of the teacher in a multimedia classroom because the slides attract you more than the lectures?

Figure 2: Slides attracts more in multimedia classroom which hampers students' understanding of the lecture.

ii. Many students often fail to take important notes from the slides due to sitting in the back or in the corners of the classroom, do you agree?

Figure 3: Sitting in the back or in the corner of the classroom creates inability of students' taking important notes.

iii. Do you think the teacher often fails to control the students in a multimedia classroom when paying more attention to the slides than keeping eye on the students?

Figure 4: Teachers' failure in controlling the students in a multimedia classroom for paying more attention on the slides.

iv. Do you think in a multimedia-aided classroom, few students lose attention after a while and start gossiping among themselves which may cause disturbance for others who are attentive in the class?

Figure 5: Gossiping of students after a while causes disturbance to others.

v. There is often not enough information in the slides as in the lecture in a multimedia classroom which makes it more difficult for the students to understand the lecture accurately. Do you agree?

Figure 6: Lack of enough information in the slides makes it more difficult for the students to understand lectures accurately.

vi. Do you believe that in a larger class, the use of an audio device like a microphone can be useful to reach the lecture to the students, which most of the private universities in Bangladesh cannot provide?

Figure 7: Inability of the private universities to providing accessory like microphone in the large classrooms in Bangladesh makes lectures less effective.

vii. In Bangladesh, many newly admitted students in private universities have lack of basic knowledge about various skills of the language like listening and writing skills which can be a barrier to being able to follow the lectures properly in a multimedia classroom. How far do you support this statement?

Figure 8: Lack of basic knowledge about various skills of language works as a barrier to follow lectures in multimedia classroom.

viii. Do you think teaching grammar through multimedia is more effective than the conventional use of board and marker?

Figure 9: Students' opinion on whether teaching grammar using multimedia is more effective than conventional board and marker.

ix. Do you think students need to get the slides or the other materials forehead to be able to understand a multimedia class thoroughly?

Figure 10: Students' opinion on whether they need to get slides or materials forehead to better understand a multimedia class.

x. Do you think that teaching every course through multimedia can be fruitful rather than using relevant texts for better understanding?

Figure 11: Students' opinion on whether teaching each courses using multimedia can be beneficial for learners.

5. Findings

The study was conducted on the University Level students from various universities (City University, Manarat University, BGMEA University of fashion and technology) in the Dhaka division. About 35.4% of students expressed that in a multimedia classroom, few students lose attention after a while and start to gossip among themselves which is a cause of disturbance for the others who are attentive in the class. On the other hand, nearly 33.5% of students disagreed with this. Approximately, 35.4% of students said that there is inadequate information in the slides of a multimedia classroom which makes it difficult for the students to understand the lecture accurately. Contrarily, 25% of students disagreed with them. 58.3% of students think that, in a large class, the use of sound equipment like a microphone can be useful to deliver the lecture to each of the students which most of the universities lack in our country. Another interesting finding is that the multiple references which the teachers refer before a multimedia class are also hard for the students of Bangladesh to understand on their own. About 50% of students agreed that teaching basic grammar rules using multimedia is more helpful than the conventional use of board and marker. About 43.7% of students agreed and 27.1% strongly agreed that students coming to get admitted to universities do not have enough basic knowledge about various skills of language like listening and reading skills and it can be a barrier in following the lectures properly in the multimedia classrooms. Nearly 50% of students agreed that they need to get slides on other materials forehand to be able to understand multimedia class. Almost 31.7% of students said that teaching every course using multimedia can be fruitful than using relevant text for better understanding but 36.6% of students disagreed with this. Most of the teachers believe that due to the imbalance of syllabus and semester-length, the class time is often very short to cover all the areas of slides which they often have to skip and as a result, it hampers the understanding of the students. Another interesting finding is that, in most cases, managing between lecture and multimedia hampers the flow of lecture which can be very much confusing for many students to be attentive spontaneously.

6. Discussion

6.1. Analysis of the questionnaire survey

Students from the university level agreed that it hampers their understanding of the lecture of the teacher in a multimedia classroom because they are always giving more attention in taking notes from the slides. Sometimes, students who have to sit in the back seats or even in the corners often fail to take the important notes from the slides which make them unable to receive the information properly hence hampers learning. In our country, students coming to get admitted in universities do not have enough basic knowledge about various skills of language like listening and reading skills and it can be a barrier in following the lectures properly in multimedia classrooms. They also opined that multimedia classes are not that much interactive like the conventional way of giving lectures.

6.2. Interview Analysis

Most of the teachers mention that using multimedia while teaching basic grammar in the classroom is helpful but using a blended learning method is the most effective way. They think that while teaching grammar, the teacher needs to write/make a number of examples to make the students understand the correct usage of grammar. Because, in this regard, the teacher might face some difficulties while making a number of changes in the same sentence during teaching a topic of grammar. But in terms of teaching literature, most of them agreed that using multimedia can be helpful for a teacher as he can show some relevant pictures and sometimes video clips related to the text. It makes the lecture more interesting and intelligible. They feel that it is a big challenge for the teachers where the number of students is really big. Teachers suggest pre-study but in most of the cases, it is seen that students attend their classes with blank heads. It really throws teachers in a very tough situation to make the class fruitful. In this case, teachers can provide some easily intelligible handouts before starting the class. Most of the teachers said that almost 99% of teachers don't know how to make PowerPoint presentations properly and use multimedia tools effectively and it is very shocking.

Figure 12 indicates teachers' opinions regarding multimedia classrooms. Their most commonly used words are "students", "multimedia" and "teachers." From the interviews of the teachers, we found their opinions

students for being attentive in the class. It will help to learn a particular topic in detail.

According to the teachers, as classes through multimedia give the scope of involving the students in different audio-visual tasks and activities, it helps to create a more responsive environment in the classrooms. Communicating in a foreign language is not a comfortable issue for the students. They lose their interest and attention very quickly. Using multimedia is helping the students to follow the class and works as an aid to the teachers to grab the attention of the students. Primary level education is far away from the multimedia facilities and is still following the traditional teaching-learning method which is still a problem. Through a multimedia class on language, a teacher can provide the students several types of content (such as audio, videos, posters, diagram, graphs, many more) that are necessary apart from showing the grammatical rules of the target language. when teachers are following a designed course structure and using the same multimedia, again and again, they are losing flexibility. On the other hand, while preparing the contents for multimedia, the teacher has a wide range of flexibility in adding or removing materials and creating variations in the content. Definitely, multimedia teaching technology is not suitable for all the courses. There are some courses that are based on critical thinking or based on the theory that required in-depth analysis. Multimedia class is not a good choice for these. Again, for the courses that need practical performance, real-life activity, critical thinking, and group discussion, multimedia technology cannot provide better support.

Figure 13 indicates the relationship TreeMap from the interviews of the teachers. When it comes to teaching grammar, using technology such as multimedia cannot be an effective tool as using multimedia only may not be sufficient. Therefore, using a whiteboard is essential when it comes to the teaching of grammar. However, multimedia can also be used with the whiteboard. Not only in the case of grammar but also in classes of literature, this juxtaposition can be followed. The relationship TreeMap highlights teachers' suggestions following which teachers can juxtapose multimedia and whiteboard and bring a balance in the traditional and technological classes which can facilitate students more than any of this one individual method of teaching can do. Moreover, they suggested that following this way students will not lose their attention from the classes. Besides, it will improve their learning. Again, there should be a scope of interaction for the students with the teachers so that they can get involved in the classes. If to

facilitate students and their learning from a multimedia class, teachers need to get proper training in using PowerPoint properly and efficiently. They need to master making slides with proper materials and supervise students from time to time. Only then it will be possible to facilitate the students and reach the targeted outcome.

Figure 13: The relationship TreeMap from the interview of teachers.

7. Recommendations

Some suggestions can be given in order to reduce the problems while using multimedia in teaching. Effective supervision and evaluation system can be established in multimedia teaching by providing training about the multimedia teaching equipment as well as quality standard evaluation of multimedia teaching.

By improving teaching ability, a good environment for teachers can be created. Supervision and evaluation of the effect of learning in the process of multimedia teaching are challenging. But it can be adaptive. Many

educational institutions in Bangladesh are using multimedia in language classes but the number is not many. If the students are not familiar with multimedia, they might get their minds deviated from the class and they can only look into the decoration of the slides, or the videos only. And a completely opposite scenario can appear if the contents of the presentation become too hard to apprehend for the students, as in a PowerPoint presentation we put fewer descriptions rather than only the main points of the topic. Wherefore, the teacher has to play an important role in preparing the contents accordingly. If the course objectives are relevant to the use of multimedia, it will improve students' learning skills. For example, listening and speaking skills can be easily improved by using multimedia. Because there is no other way of familiarizing them with the correct pronunciation. But for the improvement of writing skills, multimedia is not strongly recommended. They may find the audio-visual tasks difficult because of their novelty. But we think these obstacles can be overcome through identifying the students' problems particularly. On the other hand, while preparing the contents for multimedia, the teacher has a wide range of flexibility in adding or removing materials and creating variations in the content. However, when multimedia is being used in the class, the board is always there for the solution to the impromptu problems or questions asked by the learners. We think a teacher has the flexibility to design and prepare the materials for multimedia classes according to his/her own way. S/he can use different sorts of materials in multimedia class where multimedia will facilitate to improve instruction efficiency without reducing flexibility. The personal strategy and teaching skills of a teacher can customize the supervision and evaluation system in the multimedia teaching process. Some tough topics can be discussed by writing on the whiteboard in detail so that students can understand those topics clearly. Teachers can use a whiteboard while using multimedia. In the scenario of Bangladesh, most of the private universities are not well equipped with teaching materials whether in the library or on the server. In order to ensure quality education, teachers need to study scholarly articles and publications which often require buying from the internet, and with poor salaries that teachers get, it becomes really unaffordable for them. Therefore, we propose that universities provide funds or directly take suggestions from them and then buy required materials from the internet.

There should be a balance between the syllabus and semester duration, so that the instructor may cover all of the sections of the slides. As a

consequence, the students' understanding of problems will be reduced. In a multimedia classroom, a large number of students is a barrier to effective teaching, so the number of learners should be controlled. Adequate projectors and computers should be available in universities so that a large number of teachers may take multimedia lessons at the same time.

Ensuring enough multimedia equipment is a must when several classes are ongoing at a time. Teachers need to have full access of using multimedia equipment in their classes to make teaching-learning fruitful and if the universities fail to provide this equipment aptly then it will be really impossible to have the targeted outcome. Such multimedia classes are enjoyable and interesting than traditional ways of teaching in most cases. Therefore, we expect universities will take the necessary measures in this regard.

8. Conclusion

The discussion of using multimedia in the classrooms for teaching English language and literature has been widespread in Bangladesh for the last few years. Teachers and students of public and private universities often discuss this matter. When it comes to the public universities where multimedia accessories are sufficient, the condition is quite the opposite in the private universities. The difference in the students' ability of understanding is also quite evident when it comes to public and private universities. Nonetheless, our focus is on the problems that teachers and students face in the private universities of Bangladesh regarding multimedia-aided classrooms. Throughout this paper, we have discussed the major issues that teachers and students often find in multimedia classrooms which hinder their teaching-learning. We believe that the utmost goal of a multimedia classroom or any classroom is to facilitate students' learning and if that is not ensured, there is no point in conducting classes whether conventional or multimedia aided. Only well-equipped classrooms, well-trained teachers, and well-planned lectures can ensure a fruitful class where students will be able to share their views and ask questions. Teachers, on the other hand, will supervise and provide required materials forehand to ensure their students' comprehensiveness for the particular multimedia classes. If the plausible solutions we have recommended can be implemented, we think that most of the problems that teachers and learners encounter within a multimedia-aided classroom will be resolved.

References

Ackerman, D. B. (1989). Intellectual and practical criteria for successful curriculum integration In H. H. Jacobs (Ed.), *Interdisciplinary Curriculum: Design and Implementation* Alexandria, VA: Association for Supervision and Curriculum Development Abowd, G. D., Atkeson, C. G., Feinstein, A., Hmelo, C., Kooper, R., Long, S., ... & Tani,

M. (1997, February). Teaching and learning as multimedia authoring: the classroom 2000 project. In *Proceedings of the fourth ACM international conference on Multimedia* (pp.187-198).

Ahmed, M. K. (2018). Multimedia Aided Language Teaching: An Ideal Pedagogy in the English Language Teaching of Bangladesh. *American International Journal of Social Science Research*, 3(1), 39-47.

Alam, M. T. (2018). The use of technology in English language teaching and learning (ELTL): Bangladesh perspective. *Research Journal of English (RJOE)*, Vol-3(4), 69-83.

Ambron, S., & Hooper, K. (1988). *Interactive multimedia*. Redmond, WA: Microsoft Publishing.

Asthana, A. (2009). Multimedia in Education - Introduction, the Elements of, Educational Requirements, Classroom Architecture and Resources, Concerns [On-line]. Available:

<http://encyclopedia.jrank.org/articles/pages/6821/Multimedia-in-Education.html>

Blin, F. (1997). CALL and the learner-centred curriculum: What about the teacher? Proceedings of *EUROCALL 96*, Hungary.

Boyce, C., & Neale, P. (2006). Conducting in-depth interviews: A guide for designing and conducting in-depth interviews for evaluation input.

Cummings, L. (1995). Educational technologyÐA faculty resistance view. Part I:

Incentives and understanding, *Educational Technology Review*, 13-18.

Cummings, L. (1996). Educational technology & faculty resistance view. Part II:

Challenges of resources, technology and tradition, *Educational Technology Review*, 30, 18-20.

Davis, F. D., Bagozzi, R. P., & Warshaw, P. R. (1989). User acceptance of computer technology: a comparison of two theoretical models. *Management science*, 35(8), 982-1003.

Fan, H. L., & Orey, M. (2001). Multimedia in the Classroom. *Journal of Research on Computing in Education*, 33(5).

Fernández Carballo-Calero, M. V. (2001). The EFL teacher and the introduction of multimedia in the classroom. *Computer Assisted Language Learning*, 14(1), 3- 14.

Hasan, M.K., Jamila F. & Sultana N. (2019). Problematic areas of ELT at Secondary Level Schools in Bangladesh: Issues and Prospectus. *International Journal of English Language Teaching*, Vol.7(6), 15-31.

Hede, T. & Hede, A. (2002). Multimedia effects on learning: Design implications of an integrated model. In McNamara, S. & Stacey, E. (Ed), *Untangling the Web: Establishing Learning Links*. Proceedings of ASET Conference 2002 [On-line].

Available: <http://www.aset.org.au/confs/2002/hede-t.html>

Jinping, Z., & Qiuping, Z. (2013). The Limitations and Application Errors in Multimedia Teaching of College. In *2012 First National Conference for Engineering Sciences (FNCES 2012)*.

Joshi, A. (2012). Multimedia: A technique in teaching process in the classrooms. *Current World Environment*, 7(1), 33.

Kasper, L. F. (1997). The impact of content-based instructional programs on the academic progress of ESL students. *English for specific purposes*, 16(4), 309-320.

Leow, F. T., & Neo, M. (2014). Interactive multimedia learning: Innovating classroom education in a Malaysian university. *Turkish Online Journal of Educational Technology-TOJET*, 13(2), 99-110.

Lincoln, Y.S., & Guba, E.G. (1985). *Naturalistic inquiry*. Newbury Park, CA: Sage.

Parekh, R. (2006). *Principles of Multimedia*. New Delhi: Tata McGraw-Hill.

Rahman, M. M. & Pandian, A. (2018). A Critical Investigation of English Language Teaching in Bangladesh. *English Today* 135, Vol. 34, No. 3.

Shank, P. (2005). The Value of Multimedia in Learning. Adobe Design Center [On-line].

Available:

http://www.adobe.com/designcenter/thinktank/valuemedia/The_Value_of_Multimedia.pdf

Surendran, P. (2012). Technology acceptance model: A survey of literature. *International Journal of Business and Social Research*, 2(4), 175-178.

Susikaran, R. S. A., & Phil, M. (2013). The use of multimedia in English language teaching. *Journal of Technology for ELT*, 3(2).

Tanguay, E. (1997). *English teachers, prepare yourselves for the digital age*, [the Internet]. Available: <http://userpage.fu-berlin.de/~tanguay/english-teachers.htm> [1998].

Zhang, Le. Analysis on the Role and Functions of Teachers, Teaching Materials and Learners in the Multimedia-aided English Classroom—Based on the Study of Linfen No.1 Senior School. *Theory and Practice in Language Studies*, Vol. 7, No. 11, pp. 1132-1138, November 2017.

Lu, Juan. The Current Problems of Multimedia-aided college English Teaching and its Countermeasures. *Advances in Social Science, Education and Humanities Research*, volume 238.